

A Comparative Evaluation of the Perspectives on Suicide of Philosophers such as Camus, Hume , Schopenhauer and Nietzsche, and the Arguments of Philosophers Who Do Not Advocate Suicide, such as Kant

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Abstract

The topic of suicide elicits contemplation as it unveils intricate inquiries that have been delineated, expounded upon, and resolved via diverse philosophical perspectives across several historical

epochs, including ruminations, literary works, ethical considerations, and philosophical discourse.

The phenomenon of suicide is characterized by a high degree of complexity and a multitude of factors that contribute to and facilitate its occurrence (Yıldırım, 2023, p. 7). To effectively analyze a philosopher's discourse on the subject of suicide, it is necessary to possess a comprehensive understanding of the historical context in which the philosopher resided, their particular viewpoint on the religious beliefs prevalent throughout their lifetime, and their broader considerations pertaining to mortality. There exists a divergence of perspectives about suicide, which may be attributed to a multitude of circumstances. Nietzsche's intellectual development was shaped by the philosophical ideas of influential thinkers such as Schopenhauer, Plato, and Descartes, which in turn inspired his own written

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works and intellectual output. The philosophical discourse about suicide was notably shaped by the religious perspectives held by many thinkers. An illustration of this scenario may be seen in the works of Kant. Kant's moral philosophy has a profound interconnection with his religious perspectives. Kant posits that our moral judgements are grounded on reason. According to the text, the presence of reasonable judgements is deemed necessary for an individual's moral conduct. It is unreasonable to anticipate that Kant's ideas can be dissociated from his reflections on the subject of suicide. Schopenhauer's philosophical views were shaped by the impact of Kant's ideas, while also expressing critical perspectives towards Kant's theories and highlighting areas of disagreement. According to Schopenhauer, a renowned philosopher, it might be argued that Kant, being a great genius, is a figure worthy of influence. The perspectives of philosophers towards suicide are neither mutually incompatible nor detached from their personal circumstances. However, while examining the works of Camus, a distinct contrast emerges in comparison to the perspective put forward by Kant. In the works

of Camus, one may see a tendency towards simplicity in his thinking. Life is not inherently imbued with profound significances. According to Camus, the significance of our existence eludes discovery within the external realm that surrounds us. The phenomenon often referred to as "nonsense" or "dissonance" might be attributed to the inherent disconnect between human cognition and the external environment. The influence of nihilism is also evident in his character. According to Hume, objects or concepts that lack a corresponding counterpart in the external world are deemed insignificant and potentially deceptive. According to Hume's teachings, it may be inferred that human conceptions are derived from human experiences and are considered to be faint imitations of those original sensory perceptions. According to his perspective, the significance is in the observations and knowledge gained through empirical investigations.

Key Words: *Suicide, Kant, Camus, Hume , Schopenhauer , Nietzsche, Morality, God, Death*

Introduction

The concept of suicide has been subject to varying interpretations among philosophers. The discourse around suicide often intersects with religious beliefs and intellectual currents prevalent during a given era. Albert Camus (1913–1960) saw suicide as a "grave issue" that encompasses many layers and numerous factors that contribute to and enable its occurrence.

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The act of suicide might potentially be influenced by a combination of several elements, such as neurobiological aspects, personal or familial history, exposure to stressful situations, and the social context in which an individual resides. The investigation of the psychological mechanisms that contribute to the emergence of suicidal ideation and behavior is a distinct area of inquiry, as it pertains to one of the most aggressive manifestations of human conduct (Yıldırım, Psychological Factors of Suicide, p. 8, 2023). There exists a multitude of perspectives and a diverse range of philosophical arguments about an individual's decision to choose the timing of their own death. In this context, Mill discusses the imperative nature of individual liberties, while Camus focuses on the concept of the ridiculous individual. Within the context of Abrahamic faiths, it is believed that life is inherently the possession of God and is seen as a sacred responsibility imbued with profound spiritual significance.

Immanuel Kant (1724-1804) had a significant impact on several figures within the annals of philosophy. His scholarly pursuits were primarily focused on the metaphysics of morality, and he demonstrated a diligent commitment to his profession. The concept of "Kantian ethics" is a well-recognized word in academic discourse. Kant argues that ethics is indispensable. Kant's philosophical framework is characterized by the establishment of a systematic structure that is derived from the faculty of reason. The foundation of morality in Kant's ethical framework is in the concept of unconditionality. According to a philosopher who emphasized the significance of seeing humanity as an aim in itself, it is inconceivable to perceive suicide as a morally justifiable act. The idea of individual agency is not isolated from other factors, thereby rendering suicide a detrimental and superfluous act. According to Immanuel Kant, an individual who engages in the act of suicide would be using humankind as a mere instrument for the sake of evading their circumstances. In the philosophical framework espoused by Kant, it may be broadly posited that the concepts of dignified respectability and suicide are fundamentally incompatible. Kant's philosophical framework distinguishes him from several other thinkers, making his ideas challenging to comprehend and analyze. Despite the presence of conflicting viewpoints, suicide remains a topic of considerable discourse in contemporary society.

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Aim

The research conducted on suicide, the philosophical discourse generated, and the foundational elements around which endeavors are constructed are undeniably vital and significant for both society and the human race. The objective of this research is to reexamine the insights that arise from juxtaposing the philosophical perspectives of eminent thinkers, including Camus, Hume, Schopenhauer, and Nietzsche, who hold significant positions in the annals of philosophy, with Kant's views on the subject of suicide. The philosophical framework developed by an individual philosopher is characterized by its distinctiveness and is shaped by the intellectual impact of other philosophers. Similar to the refined and purified nature of contemporary honey and processed foods, many philosophical ideas undergo a transformative process, spanning over generations, minds, written texts, and ultimately, the repositories that our visual perception and cognitive faculties engage with. The objective of this research is to conduct a comparative and evaluative analysis of the viewpoints held by philosophers, like Camus, Hume, Schopenhauer, and Nietzsche, who did not see suicide as inherently negative, in contrast to philosophers like Kant, who always held a negative stance against suicide, regardless of the rationale.

Method

The present work has been generated using a compilation approach, whereby data and information from many available sources were rigorously collected and analyzed. The research focuses on the topic of suicide. The history of the philosophy of humanity is akin to a rich mine, encompassing both profound and illuminating ideas. It comprises the intellectual contributions of diverse philosophers who, despite their exceptional insights, remain inherently human. This field draws upon a wide array of scholarly sources, including research articles, scarce but invaluable books, and information derived from other written works. The objective of this synthesis is to give a holistic viewpoint. The purpose of the review methodology is to include

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a broad array of scholarly literature pertaining to the topic at hand, with the intention of offering a thorough comprehension by amalgamating diverse viewpoints.

Arthur Schopenhauer and Suicide

In the case of Schopenhauer (1788 - 1860), it is evident that he adopts a distinct viewpoint while examining the concept of suicide. According to his perspective, suicide is not considered a means of salvation, nor can moralistic approaches effectively deter it. According to Schopenhauer, suicide does not arise from the suppression of desire; rather, it emerges as a response to the intense yearning and hope for circumstances that lie beyond the realm of attainability. Schopenhauer's moral teachings do not include the topic of suicide, and he expresses strong disapproval towards those who promote suicide based on moral grounds. It is well acknowledged that Stoics may extol suicide and laud it as a virtuous and valorous deed. Schopenhauer refutes the stoic ethical system that endorses suicide on the grounds that, in his view, suicide does not constitute a means of redemption. (Schopenhauer, 2020, pp. 522, 65) According to the philosophical perspective put forward by Schopenhauer, it is posited that the mortality of human beings is an inevitable reality, since human existence is inherently susceptible to the inevitability of death. Furthermore, Schopenhauer argues that human life lacks any inherent superiority or inherent dignity. Is it possible to prevent suicide? Schopenhauer contends that the prevention of suicide cannot be achieved by the adherence to moral principles or the reliance on religious beliefs. Monotheistic faiths often see suicide as a transgression or moral offense. Nevertheless, he contends that those who serve as representatives of religious beliefs are unable to provide a persuasive response to the inquiry about the reasons why one should refrain from engaging in suicidal behavior. This factor maybe contributed to Schopenhauer's atheistic beliefs. Schopenhauer posits that it is imperative to question the assertion made by the representatives of the Abrahamic religions who categorize and denounce the act of suicide, which elicits sentiments of compassion and empathy within

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us, as a criminal act. Schopenhauer refutes the doctrines and tenets advocated by proponents of faith, particularly those associated with monotheistic faiths. Schopenhauer's stance on suicide is not explicitly supportive, although it does not outright denounce the act. What is your perspective on those who engage in the act of suicide? Schopenhauer contends that it is morally erroneous to stigmatize those who engage in suicide and to confine them to a negative realm within our collective consciousness. Simultaneously, the individual holds the belief that suicide does not serve as a means of redemption or escape. According to Schopenhauer, the attribution of meaning to life entails a process of concealing its inherent nature. Furthermore, Schopenhauer sees human being not as a source of prestige, but rather as a manifestation of benevolence, sympathy, or understanding that diminishes and renders the barrier between individuals permeable. In contrast, Kant used a subjective approach to the human mind. He classified the mind within the realms of the soul, the world, and God. Kant saw God as the fundamental determinant of both the individual soul and the external universe. He said that both entities were intricacies of the human intellect, and posited that no individual has the ability to transcend this situation. Kant conducted an analysis of antinomies, while demonstrating that material entities possess the capacity for abstract thought. The concept of antinomies encompasses four fundamental categories: quantity, quality, connection, and modality. Schopenhauer expresses dissent against Kant's ideas, seeing the antinomies superfluous and devoid of meaning. According to the philosopher Schopenhauer, the whole of an individual's perceptual experience may be attributed to the faculty of imagination. The perception of the world is subjective and varies from one to individual. According to the individual in question, the universe is contingent upon the subject, since it is essentially the perception that is being perceived by the perceiver. Given the prevalence of suicide in contemporary society, it may be inferred that suicide is a phenomenon that is both perceptible and conceptual in nature.

Albert Camus and Suicide

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According to the renowned philosopher Albert Camus (1913-1960), the optimal approach to living is to embrace the inherent lack of purpose in life since it allows for a more fulfilling existence. What is the existential significance of human existence? Why do individuals ascribe significance to existence despite their awareness of mortality? What are the primary concerns or fundamental issues within the field of philosophy that are often regarded as significant? The individual in question did not specifically broach the topic of suicide; nonetheless, the concept of suicide emerged prominently within the discourse about the inherent conflict between life and death. According to Camus, the singularly significant philosophical quandary is in the contemplation of suicide. According to Camus (2014, p. 21),... The significance of suicide as a pressing issue is evident in his perception, as shown by this line. Camus adopts an individualistic perspective in his exploration of suicide, focusing on its personal dimensions rather than seeing it as a collective or societal event. The prominence of the notion of the ridiculous becomes evident in relation to Camus and the topic of suicide. According to the philosophical perspective of Albert Camus, the issue of suicide may be comprehended within the framework of the ridiculous, whereby the essence of human life is revealed and made palpable. According to the individual in question, it is important to approach the notion of the ludicrous in a conceptual manner and strive to achieve mental clarity in order to effectively address the issue of suicide and prevent its lingering unresolved state. Individuals who engage in the act of suicide have the belief that they have discovered a truth of such significance that it justifies the termination of their own existence. Indeed, individuals who engage in suicidal behavior often see that the same motivations that give them a sense of purpose in life may simultaneously serve as the impetus for their self-inflicted demise. According to Camus, the first inquiry that must be addressed initially is to the significance of existence. (Camus, 2005, p. 2) Albert Camus provides a lucid elucidation of the existential inquiries surrounding the purpose of human existence and the act of self-inflicted death. There exists a correlation between the existential significance of life and the realm of scientific inquiry, while the latter finds some impediments at some point. According to Camus, scientific disciplines too undergo a transformative process, becoming entangled in a particular context and ultimately dissipating

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within that process. In essence, an individual has the potential to maintain a state of unfamiliarity with both their own nature and the external environment. Camus acquaints readers with the concept of dualism and directs their attention towards the inherent contradictions present within the words he composes. Diametric occurrences such as the existence and cessation of life, the experience of joy and sadness, and the presence and absence of darkness and light... The concepts of life and death... Individuals enhance the significance of their existence by the act of existing, so imbuing life with meaning. However, concurrently, they possess an awareness of their inevitable mortality. The persistence of this paradox is deemed illogical. If a someone has the awareness that their existence lacks purpose and is devoid of value, should they contemplate ending their own life? The circumstances at hand might potentially constitute a tragic cycle for Albert Camus. The author has previously used the notion of absurdity in this context. The author refers to the concept of absurdity in relation to the presence of contradictions and paradoxes within a given circumstance. There exists a facet of existence that should not be taken lightly. However, it is important to note that Camus should not be seen as a proponent of suicide. The individual has an understanding of the inherent lack of purpose in life and acknowledges the impossibility of eradicating this existential dilemma. However, they express a reluctance to be left behind in the struggle against this inherent contradiction. The current configuration of the universe is not inherently conducive to the human cognitive framework, rendering it illogical in nature. According to Camus' philosophical reflections, the inherent essence of existence renders all significance futile. According to the philosopher Albert Camus, the act of ending one's own life cannot be justified by any means, even justifications based on facts or truths. What kind of reconciliation need to be established between the concept of quality of life and the notion of absurdity? According to the philosophical ideas put out by Camus, the essence of existence does not lie in its inherent significance, but rather in its inherent absurdity. The individual who lacks alignment with the purpose of being, but instead finds solace inside their own ego, might be characterized as an absurd person. The notion of the ridiculous encompasses several interpretations, including the metaphorical representation of a worm residing inside an individual, namely within their heart,

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gradually consuming them internally. This imagery symbolizes the existential anguish experienced by individuals due to the inherent lack of inherent purpose ascribed to existence, which perpetuates a persistent sense of unease within them. The phenomenon often referred to as life lacks inherent purpose and is impervious to annihilation based on purpose. Albert Camus, a renowned philosopher, once expressed the notion that life had no inherent meaning. In his perspective, he advocated for a conscientious approach to living one's life. The individual asserts and presents the argument that the temporal nature of human existence renders the pursuit of meaning futile, positing that life inherently lacks inherent significance. Furthermore, the individual contends that even if life has a discernible purpose, it will not provide any transformative effects. According to the individual's perspective, it may be argued that the optimal course of action for an individual is to actively engage in the experience of living their life. According to Camus, existence lacks inherent purpose. However, he posits that engaging with experiences devoid of meaning might still have value if approached in a meaningful manner. Individuals contemplating suicide often have the belief that life has inherent value that is independent of their existence. Camus discusses the concept of the ridiculous individual, referring to an individual who embraces the view that existence lacks inherent significance. Rather of engaging in self-harm, an individual has the potential to cultivate cognitive processes that align with societal norms, adapt to their circumstances, and focus on the current moment. Camus refers to this particular predicament as a kind of reasoning that is characterized by its absurdity. Have you ever had a sense of temporal indebtedness or seen time as existing autonomously from your own being? In the realm of Camus' philosophy, those who see time as existing independently from their own existence hold the belief that they are entitled to a portion of this endless continuum, since they perceive it to be everlasting. These individuals see time as a debtor and establish a duration for their existence. These individuals strategically design and choose the life they believe they are entitled to and have consciously selected for themselves. Frequently, they assert that they possess enough time due to their youthfulness or lament the scarcity of time remaining in light of their advanced age. To get insight into the concept of suicide in the works of Albert Camus, it is essential to analyze the cognitive

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framework of the individual who embodies the philosophy of the ridiculous. What are the characteristics of an individual who embodies absurdity? The individual in question demonstrates a lifestyle characterized by actively managing time, rather than passively depending on, or becoming complacent inside it. Therefore, the individual characterized by absurdity does not possess the attribute of temporality. One of the factors contributing to individuals deviating from temporal constraints is their adherence to religious faith. According to the philosophical perspective of Albert Camus, an individual who embraces the concept of God experiences a detachment from the temporal dimension. Given the everlasting nature of God, humanity acknowledges and seeks reconciliation. Based on an analysis of Camus' literary works, it becomes evident that the ridiculous individual has a profound aversion towards aligning oneself with the eternal. Moreover, this individual is inherently incompatible with any kind of timeless or superhuman entities.

Consequently, the philosophical principles elucidated by Schopenhauer and Camus suggest that the significance of life is in the very process of a person's physical decay, regardless of whether one contemplates or tries to engage in self-inflicted mortality. Specifically, individuals of average status possess the ability to establish a personal link with the concepts of life and death, often without any effort, and often fail to recognize the existence of this relationship. According to Camus, the attribution of responsibility for suicide episodes in society is promptly determined, with an individual being identified as the cause or perpetrator of this act. Nevertheless, it is important to note that this particular factor does not serve as the primary cause of suicide, but rather functions as a catalyst. (Camus, 2014, p. 23) is a citation indicating a specific page in a publication by Camus. The lack of comprehension on this matter is the primary reason security forces and judicial authorities are often the last entities involved in the investigation of suicide cases. In a society presumed to be well-known, it is very astonishing when individuals who are recognized abruptly terminate their own lives. This is due to the fact that individuals contemplating or desiring to engage in suicidal behavior often do it in a clandestine manner rather than publicly. The act of preparing for suicide encompasses more

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than the actual efforts to end one's life. There is an increased likelihood of fatality associated with suicide attempts. The absence of a suicide attempt does not always indicate the absence of a desire for death in an individual. One of the fundamental motivations underpinning individuals' inclination towards suicide is the need to attain an eternal and blissful state inside the cycle of existence. Individuals who see themselves as having exhausted a wide range of life experiences, as well as those who believe they have still to encounter significant experiences, may resort to suicide for similar underlying motivations. The first individual succumbed to nostalgia, whereas the subsequent individual met their demise due to hope. If one were to consider a fundamental verity about existence, it would be the assertion made by Camus that all individuals are subject to victimhood and inevitably confront mortality. The only variable that undergoes change within this phase pertains to the causes or agents of mortality. Camus, a prominent advocate, consistently underscores the notion that human life is inherently burdened by the inevitability of mortality. However, it is crucial to note that this perspective does not imply an endorsement of self-inflicted demise. Furthermore, Camus places significant emphasis on the role of art in his philosophical framework. An individual who successfully endures is someone who actively safeguards and protects the preservation of life. These aforementioned attributes pertain to the individual who embodies the concept of the ridiculous. He has the ability to initiate a fresh beginning, even in the face of several challenges that others may see as potential catalysts for suicidal ideation.

Consequently, Albert Camus proposes a set of attitudes that may be cultivated in order to address the issue of suicide. These include the endeavor to acknowledge the inherent absurdity of existence, extending one's waking hours, fostering an open and receptive mindset, nurturing a yearning for vitality and expansiveness, relinquishing the longing for ultimate coherence and certainty, abstaining from surrendering to habitual routines, refusing to be confined by the constraints of time, and rejecting the notion of living as if perpetually on the brink of death. Contemplating the inherent mortality of the human condition and deriving solace from engaging

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with artistic mediums such as works of art, theatrical performances, and literary narratives may potentially contribute to the amelioration of the issue of suicide.

Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche and Suicide

In Nietzsche's philosophical discourse, the concept of suicide is seen as a deliberate act of self-inflicted mortality. Furthermore, although Nietzsche engages with the notion of virtue, his exploration reveals that its underlying principles and origins may be traced back to various manifestations of power. According to Friedrich Nietzsche, a renowned philosopher known for his unconventional perspectives and critique of Christianity, the act of voluntarily ending one's life under some circumstances, in alignment with the pursuit of the will to power, might be seen as a virtuous endeavor.

Nietzsche consistently advocated for the preservation and affirmation of life. Nietzsche vehemently attacked those who venerate death, extol death, and hold disdain for life without due regard. He endorses the act of suicide with the stipulation that it is carried out with the intention of enhancing the worth of life and exalting its significance. Individuals that possess a strong inclination towards exerting power and generating significant values are a rare occurrence within society. The group in question represents a smaller proportion than the minority alluded to by Nietzsche in his own writings. In communities characterized by herd morality, individuals who deviate from societal norms may face marginalization, perhaps leading to a diminished sense of purpose and value in their lives. According to Nietzsche's writings on suicide, it may be inferred that those who are marginalized and ostracized have the option to see death as a virtuous alternative when circumstances deem their existence to be devoid of value. In pursuit of the elevated human concept and guided by a morally upright disposition, individuals exhibit a preference for suicide, or as Nietzsche articulates it, voluntary death. Individuals may choose to detach themselves from the prevailing views and values of the dominant social group, opting instead to prioritize their own thoughts and convictions.

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Nietzsche's stance on suicide posits the notion that the master's useful and abbreviated existence is more desirable in comparison to the protracted but debased life of the slave. Who has the position of authority in this context? A select minority of individuals with distinct personal convictions and perspectives that are often seen as peripheral or even outright rejected by the majority. The individual in question, as depicted in Nietzsche's verses, is a person subjected to the condition of slavery. The dominating and like-minded majority segment of society is prevalent. Might he possibly be alluding to those who espouse the Christian faith? According to Friedrich Nietzsche, the duration of an individual's existence in the world has little significance if their life is deemed unimportant and devoid of value. The fundamental consideration lies in an individual's pursuit of a virtuous existence within the confines of our earthly realm. A death that has significance and worth, ultimately concluding an individual's existence, might be seen as a death that occurs at an appropriate moment. The demise of an individual who has failed to provide significance and purpose to their own existence might be seen as an abrupt and premature passing, regardless of the timing. According to Nietzsche, the apprehension of death is seen superfluous since it represents the ultimate termination of one's existence. The notion of embracing death as a transformative experience, coupled with a belief in an afterlife or other realm, does not alleviate individuals' apprehension about mortality. Moreover, this perspective renders the present world devoid of significance. According to the individual's perspective, the belief in the continuation of life after death implies a lack of belief in the concept of mortality. According to Nietzsche, this worldview exhibits a contradiction. According to Nietzsche, the notion that earthly existence would be met with either heavenly or hellish consequences in the hereafter has resulted in individuals being confined by the dread of death and has transformed their present lives into a state of confinement. According to Nietzsche, it is possible to intentionally inflict damage onto the most virtuous aspect of an individual under certain circumstances. According to Friedrich Nietzsche, it is conceivable that an individual may ultimately contemplate suicide as a result of their pursuit of the will to power, or alternatively, they may choose to selflessly devote themselves in the pursuit of power. Within the realm of philosophical contemplation, it becomes evident that an individual's eminence or

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magnificence might concurrently manifest as their propensity for cruelty or their willingness to make profound sacrifices, even to the extent of forfeiting their own life. Individuals who are compelled to sacrifice their lives as a consequence of their formidable will for dominance serve as exemplars for Nietzsche's notion of the exceptional human being. Nietzsche posits that the will to power has significant importance, serving as the fundamental driving force behind human existence. Moreover, he contends that the ultimate aim of life and virtue lies in perpetually augmenting the desire to power, even to the extent of being willing to sacrifice one's life in its pursuit when circumstances demand. According to the philosophical views of Friedrich Nietzsche, the act of voluntarily ending one's life in pursuit of the ideal of the higher human might be seen as an instance of noble conduct. Nietzsche posits that the act of suicide, undertaken in pursuit of one's will to power, has a heroic quality. However, irrespective of prevailing circumstances, life retains inherent value. Hence, individuals are compelled to exert efforts in safeguarding their own life.

David Hume and Suicide

The posthumous publication of David Hume's article titled "Suicide" and his work known as "Five Theses" occurred subsequent to the author's death. Hume's critique of religion, characterized by his distinctive approach, was accompanied by an extensive examination of many occurrences, including suicide.

According to Hume, matters pertaining to religion and the divine are, as he himself describes, an enigma or even an inscrutable phenomenon that defies rational explanation. This perspective links the results of humanity's quest for religion and the divine with feelings of apprehension and ambiguity. The presence of the notion of suicide cannot be assumed to have been eradicated from these thoughts. David Hume critiques a well-known philosophical comparison, asserting

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the inadequacy of likening the human-inhabited cosmos to a machine. He rejects the notion that the universe, like to machines, was fashioned by a divine creator. It may be inferred from this line of reasoning that a comprehensive assessment of his evaluations pertaining to suicide is warranted. The individual in question is a highly focused philosopher who places significant emphasis on the inherent self-centeredness shown by human beings. According to the individual in question, all aspects of human development follow a distinct trajectory, and they express a lack of interest in both fatalism and determinism. In a broad sense, it might be posited that all phenomena can be classified as human events. Numerous choices, such as the determination to engage in self-harm or the will to continue living, are intricately linked to the cognitive processes involved in human decision-making. Hume's works reveal his approach to the concept of suicide as one characterized by a critical inquiry coupled with a tendency to normalize its occurrence. According to the philosopher David Hume, suicide might be seen as a potential choice available to individuals. Furthermore, in the event that an individual's existence lacks value and serves as a source of suffering, it becomes devoid of purpose for this individual to persist in existing. According to the philosophical perspective of Hume, the act of suicide does not inherently render an individual morally reprehensible or culpable. This is due to the belief that human beings lack the capacity to disturb the natural order by means of self-inflicted death.

If suicide is seen to be a criminal act, it would imply a transgression of our moral obligations towards God, our fellow human beings, and ourselves. David Hume, a renowned philosopher, approaches the topic of suicide with a profound level of consideration, attributing significant philosophical significance to this act. There are measures that acknowledge and address the issue of suicide.

Is it not the case that every person have the right to terminate their own life? Would he not be using the inherent abilities bestowed upon him by nature in compliance with legal regulations?

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The text discusses the act of departing from one's assigned responsibilities in the presence of emotional distress and sorrow. To what extent did human agency and divine intervention shape the course of destiny? Where does humanity fit into the predetermined course set by a divine entity? In the process of examining these inquiries, the topic of suicide is addressed. Consequently, in order to comprehend Hume's position on suicide, it becomes imperative to scrutinize these questions and responses through his lens and interpret them accordingly.

Suicide from the Viewpoint of John Stuart Mill

The concept of freedom refers to the state or condition of being able to act, speak, or think without any external constraints or limitations. It is a fundamental and multifaced; according to the renowned philosopher John Stuart Mill (1806 - 1873), the concept of freedom has an essential status. According to Mill, freedom may be seen as an individual's capacity to exercise choice, whereas subjecting oneself to enslavement is associated with a multitude of adverse implications. The act of suicide restricts an individual's range of choices. The act of suicide results in the termination of one's existence. Mill emphasizes the significance of pleasure or happiness. A comprehensive comprehension of utilitarianism, namely John Stuart Mill's utilitarian moral framework, will be crucial in the interpretation of suicide. A positive association exists between engaging in moral actions and experiencing a heightened sense of happiness. In his perspective, the act of imposing limitations on individual liberties is seen morally reprehensible. According to the philosopher John Stuart Mill, if the act of suicide by an individual were to result in the overall increase of pleasure or benefit for a larger number of others, such an occurrence may be considered morally permissible and beneficial. This act of suicide may be seen as a moral action. It is evident that suicide, deemed irrational by Kant, might possess moral implications provided certain requisite circumstances are satisfied, as argued by Mill.

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Suicide on the Axis of Immanuel Kant

Naturally, it would be unreasonable to anticipate that a philosopher who has forged a distinct correlation between rationality and ethical principles would endorse the validation of a peripheral notion like suicide. Immanuel Kant (1724 - 1804) has a significant and enduring position in the annals of philosophy, exerting a profound influence on subsequent thinkers whose arguments often trace their origins back to his seminal ideas. According to Kant, the act of suicide is inherently immoral and cannot be justified under any circumstances. Kant's moral theory was shaped by the philosophical tenets of Stoicism. Comprehending the works of Kant, as well as some arguments posited by the philosopher, is a considerable challenge. This difficulty arises from the presence of nuanced perspectives and unresolved facets that extend beyond a simplistic dichotomy of black and white. Kant posits that the presence of reason and virtue is contingent upon the continued existence of human beings. The act of suicide does not allow an individual to maintain their reason and morality. Can death be seen as a potential resolution? According to Immanuel Kant, death does not serve as a resolution to any of an individual's predicaments. Contrarily, the act of self-destruction by suicide effectively eradicates the potential for resolving one's own challenges. In contrast to the Stoic thinkers, Kant posits that the capacity for people to align their actions with their inherent nature persists as long as humans continue to exist. Individuals who choose to terminate their lives as a means of evading a life characterized by immorality possess a flawed perception on the trajectory of their destiny. It is impossible for an individual to possess knowledge of future events. The act of suicide cannot be motivated by apprehension for future circumstances. According to Kant, individuals facing challenging and inescapable circumstances in life must not resort to suicide. Instead, they are morally obligated to strive for the possibility of leading a decent existence. According to Kantian philosophy, individuals need to evaluate the subjective principle behind their acts in light of the categorical imperative, as opposed to focusing on the anticipated good or bad outcomes and attempting to mitigate the negative consequences. According to the philosophical perspective of Immanuel Kant, it is posited that regardless of the challenges and adversities faced in life, the attainment of one's goal and the cultivation of a

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virtuous existence remain feasible as long as one is alive. Suicide is a behavior that is in conflict with an individual's inherent, psychological, and societal dimensions. Ending one's own life is considered ethically reprehensible in any situations.

Conclusion

The topic of suicide is being addressed. An individual's inclination to depart from their present location, existence, and physical form due to many motivations... While some individuals see it as a fundamental entitlement, others view it as a moral transgression, a commendable attribute, or even a pathological condition. Kant's distinctiveness lies in his belief that suicide is inherently immoral under all circumstances. The inclusion of suicide inside the intricate framework of human life, which is not readily comprehensible, together with its distinct mathematical properties, does not provide a coherent depiction. The act of suicide is a phenomenon that is accessible to individuals, much like the inherent freedom possessed by human beings. The concept of suicide, much to art, is subjective and open to interpretation. The topic at hand pertains to the concepts of choice, philosophical trajectories, and ultimate outcomes. The subject of suicide is often discussed in terms of the interplay between pleasure and sadness, attracting those who possess a mindset akin to a swirling vortex or an exuberant celebration. After the conclusion of the wedding ceremony, individuals may exhibit divergent emotional responses, with some individuals experiencing feelings of melancholy while others get pleasure from the event. While Mevlana perceives death as a metaphorical union, it is important to acknowledge that for others, it may be seen as a tragic event. While it is true that not every death may be classified as suicide, it is important to note that every instance of suicide does result in a loss of life. The perception of suicide can vary depending on one's perspective. It may evoke contrasting images, such as the unpleasant odor of decaying fish emanating from a garbage bin while traversing a lengthy and dimly lit path, or the serene countenance of a peacefully slumbering individual who has permanently relinquished their burdens and

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deteriorating physical form. Is there uniformity among all individuals? Is it possible for all individuals to see and analyze challenges from a unified perspective and with a shared viewpoint? While some individuals exhibit unwavering resilience, steadfastly safeguarding their moral integrity even in the face of adversity, others may find themselves grappling with doubts about their virtue when confronted with overwhelming challenges, feeling vulnerable and exposed, physically and emotionally battered.

Within the realm of philosophy, there exists a dichotomy of perspectives about the concept of suicide. On one hand, some philosophers see suicide as a predicament or challenge, while on the other hand, there are others who understand suicide as a commendable trait or moral virtue. The topic of suicide is a subject of extensive discourse, encompassing a broad range of perspectives and considerations. It has been a matter of contemplation for centuries, exhibiting both subjective and contextual dimensions. It can be examined independently of religious beliefs, while also being influenced by religious ideologies. The comprehensive exploration of suicide necessitates a multifaceted approach, beginning with a humanitarian perspective and subsequently delving into its psychological, sociological, theological, and philosophical dimensions.

Prominent philosophers, including Albert Camus, Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche, David Hume, and Arthur Schopenhauer, have extensively explored the topic of suicide. Contrary to conventional perspectives, these philosophers did not adopt a negative stance towards suicide, refraining from outright condemnation. In fact, some of these philosophers even acknowledged the positive dimensions of suicide and ascribed virtue to it. According to Camus, suicide can be viewed as a potential resolution to the existential dilemmas faced by individuals. Hume, on the other hand, posits that suicide can serve as a means to attain happiness and security. Schopenhauer accepts suicide as a means to escape the suffering inherent in a life deemed devoid of value. Nietzsche, in his perspective, regards suicide as a fundamental right, privilege, and potential solution for individuals. This phenomenon may be likened as a gift. When contemplating the concept of nothingness, Friedrich Nietzsche often comes to mind. According

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to the philosophical perspectives of Nietzsche, Camus, and their adherents, the act of suicide might be seen as an expression of liberation from the existential void. From which location? To them, the perception of all things is characterized by a sense of existential emptiness. However, according to Kant's perspective, this is not the case. The act of suicide lacks positive functions and does not possess utility. According to Kant, who has distinct perspectives from other philosophers, morality, virtue, and the concept of striving are of significant importance. Kant asserts that engaging in conduct that is deemed immoral and repugnant is inherently objectionable, regardless of the rationale behind it. The act of suicide is considered morally prohibited by religious doctrine due to its repugnant and animalistic nature.

Within the realm of philosophical discourse surrounding suicide, one encounters proponents who argue for the act of suicide, presenting their own distinct arguments, as well as adversaries who oppose suicide, offering their own valid justifications.

The inclusion of notable philosophers in the discourse encompasses prominent figures such as Thomas Aquinas, Augustine of Hippo, Immanuel Kant, and, to a certain extent, John Stuart Mill, who is subject to some controversy. The legitimacy of suicide as a question of human choice is acknowledged by certain individuals. According to Yildirimer (2023), an examination of the psychological factors associated with suicide is presented on page 145.

Advocates of this perspective contend that individuals should not be compelled to endure adverse circumstances against their will, particularly in cases when there is no prospect of recuperation, such as terminal illnesses, mental disorders, and advanced age. The proponents of this perspective challenge the notion that suicide is universally illogical, positing instead that it might serve as a legitimate last option for those who have endured significant suffering or trauma. (Yildirimer, 2023)

Gaining a comprehensive understanding of suicide necessitates the identification of distinct psychological traits that may contribute to the effectiveness of prevention, intervention, and

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programmatic efforts. According to Yıldırım's research on the psychological factors of suicide (2023, p. 20), it is evident that some psychological variables have a significant role in the occurrence of suicidal behaviors.

The individuals responsible for the construction of the pyramids had a strong belief in the deity associated with the sun and the divine authority bestowed upon this celestial entity. In the absence of adherence to these ideas, it is plausible that some individuals within their ranks may have resorted to self-inflicted mortality. The presence of the pyramids we see may perhaps be considered contextually appropriate.

The interplay between philosophers' worldviews and arguments pertaining to suicide cannot be disregarded. It is evident that these two aspects have had mutual effect on one another, often leading to the presentation of contrasting theses.

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